

Increase in Air Conditioning Energy Consumption with Each Centigrade

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO
Residential Buildings in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

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Abstract

The common belief is that each degree Celsius of air conditioning setting changes energy consumption by 7%-8%.

This opinion is based on heat exchange only and does not take into account the increase in air conditioning hours with each degree.

A dynamic simulation based on real meteorological data for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv shows that the increased cooling hours component adds more energy consumption than the heat exchange component.

The analysis shows that the change with each 1°C in the range 27°C-16°C is 80%-10%/°C (average 35%/°C) in Jerusalem, and 27%-8%/°C (average 14%/°C) in Tel Aviv. The change between 27°C and 26°C is much higher than between 17°C and 16°C (for cooling).

The average increase in air conditioning energy consumption with each degree Celsius in the range 26°C-22°C – Jerusalem and Tel Aviv is 33%/°C.

The online simulation program is available at (free, no login required):

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

Glossary

$\Delta E\%$	increase of air conditioning energy consumption with 1°C change of setpoint
$\Delta HX\%$	increase of heat exchange energy with 1°C change of setpoint
$\Delta hr\%$	increase of cooling hours with 1°C change of setpoint
Ave	average
Cool On	air conditioning setpoint (also CoolT), °C
ECW	air conditioning energy consumption for cooling and condense, kWh/y
hrC	cooling hours, hr/y

Common Opinion

The common opinion of air conditioning engineers is that decreasing the thermostat setpoint by 1°C increases the energy consumption by 7%.

This opinion is expressed in the publication "*The comfort and energy impact of overcooled buildings in warm climates*" [1] as follows:

"Average reduction in cooling energy demand in warm climates is around 7% for every 1 °C rise in the setpoint temperature".

The official recommendations of the Israeli Ministry of Energy for energy conservation measures in air conditioning systems [2] indicate 8%:

"An increase of one degree in heating or a decrease in cooling may increase consumption by approximately 8%".

Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Program (BESOO)

Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Online (BESOO) is a dynamic program that calculates heat transfer through the layers of outside walls. The program applies a year's worth of actual data of ambient air temperature, relative humidity, and solar radiation to outside walls [3][4]. The 10-minute meteorological data are for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv from February 2023 to February 2024. The integration interval is 10 seconds.

The current version (544) is mainly dedicated to Heat Index and overcooling calculations [5].

Table 1 - BESOO v544 input data and default values – Jerusalem [5]

choose direction of part 1:	ESS
choose direction of part 2:	SWW
Cool On temperature	26 °C
infiltration - number of changes per hour	0.1 V/hr
ventilation - number of changes per hour	7 V/hr
activation of ventilation Δ (Troom - Ta) >	1 °C
height between floors (outside)	3.00 m
room height (inside)	2.65 m
floor length of outside wall part 1	10 m
floor length of outside wall part 2	10 m
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100 m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.020 m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200 m
inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0 m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015 m
do you want each 10min results on screen and CSV file 52,000 lines (takes time)? (1=Yes, 0=No)	0

Table 2 - BESOO v544 example of results table for default values – Jerusalem [5]

21/11/2025 03:46:00 NY			
nowagreen.ct.ws BESOO page 544Jm, v F544Jm01 Comfort Heat Index (CHI), unlimited cooling period thermostatic control			
CoolT	26	°C	Cool On
URL	https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm		
Integration Interval	10	sec	dtau
Thermal Time Constant	109.61	hours	TTC
start day	20230207		
last day	20240206		
simulation days	365		
simulation hours	8760		100%
Cooling			
cooling start date	20230517		
cooling end date	20231028		
cooling hours in the simulation period	796		9%
thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)	297	kWh thermal	50%
quantity of condense during cooling	432	liter of water	
cooling energy for condense	297	kWh thermal	50%
thermal energy for cooling and for condense	595	kWh thermal	100%
Max 10min Cool power [W thermal]	767	20230908	19:40
Max 10min power for condense [W thermal]	1246	20230813	20:10
Max 10min power for cooling and for condense	1833	20230725	19:10
HI = Heat Index			
Ave Heat Index (HI) in cooling hours	25.66	°C	AveHIC
duration of Heat Index in cooling hours	801	hours	9%
Max Heat Index in cooling hours °C	28.19	20230813	20:10
Min Heat Index in cooling hours °C	24.92	20230728	11:20
Ave Heat Index above Comfort HI (CHI) in cooling hours	27.45	°C	AveHICup
duration of Heat Index above CHI in cooling hours	11	hours	0%
Ave Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	25.63	°C	AveHICdn
duration of Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	790	hours	9%
HIO = (HI>CHI) not in Cooling hours			
Ave HIO above CHI	27.47	°C	AveHIO
duration of HIO above CHI	3	hours	0%
Max HIO above CHI °C	28.18	20230813	20:30
Ventilation			
ventilation hours	3034	hours	35%
Comfort hours			
comfort hours without cooling	7964	hours	91%
comfort hours without cooling or ventilation	4930	hours	56%

The BESOO programs are available online (free, login not required):

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544Jm>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/544TA>

Energy, Cooling Hours and Heat Exchange

Chart 1 - Energy [kWh thermal/y] and cooling hours [hr/y] at cooling setpoints 27°C–16°C - Jerusalem [5]

Chart 2 - Energy [kWh thermal/y] and cooling hours [hr/y] at cooling setpoints 27°C–16°C – Tel Aviv [5]

Formula 1 - Energy, cooling hours and heat exchange change with 1 Centigrade of setpoint

$$(1 + \Delta E\%) = (1 + \Delta hr\%) * (1 + \Delta HX\%)$$

$$\Delta HX\% = ((1 + \Delta E\%) / (1 + \Delta hr\%)) - 1$$

$\Delta E\%$ increase of air conditioning energy consumption with 1°C change of setpoint

$\Delta hr\%$ increase of cooling hours with 1°C change of setpoint

$\Delta HX\%$ increase of heat exchange energy with 1°C change of setpoint

Table 3 - Energy, cooling hours and heat exchange, %/°C – Jerusalem [5]

Cool On °C	ECW kWh/y	$\Delta E\%/^{\circ}C$	hrC hr/y	$\Delta hr\%/^{\circ}C$	$\Delta HX\%/^{\circ}C$
16	8,004	10.1%	5,473	7.7%	2.2%
17	7,270	11.9%	5,081	8.4%	3.3%
18	6,495	14.0%	4,689	10.2%	3.5%
19	5,697	18.1%	4,256	12.0%	5.5%
20	4,823	26.3%	3,800	16.0%	8.9%
21	3,818	32.4%	3,276	21.2%	9.2%
22	2,884	36.8%	2,702	27.2%	7.5%
23	2,108	42.2%	2,124	30.1%	9.3%
24	1,482	49.7%	1,632	38.5%	8.1%
25	990	66.4%	1,178	48.0%	12.4%
26	595	82.5%	796	63.4%	11.7%
27	326		487		
Ave		35.5%		25.7%	7.4%

Chart 3 - Energy, cooling hours and heat exchange, %/°C – Jerusalem [5]

Table 4 - Energy, cooling hours and heat exchange, %/°C - Tel Aviv [5]

Cool On °C	ECW kWh/y	ΔE%/°C	hrC hr/y	Δhr%/°C	ΔHX%/°C
16	12,200	7.6%	6,703	6.3%	1.3%
17	11,337	8.4%	6,307	7.0%	1.3%
18	10,461	9.3%	5,895	8.3%	0.9%
19	9,574	9.9%	5,444	8.5%	1.3%
20	8,713	10.8%	5,017	9.1%	1.6%
21	7,865	12.2%	4,599	10.1%	1.9%
22	7,007	14.1%	4,177	11.4%	2.4%
23	6,139	15.6%	3,749	12.2%	3.0%
24	5,309	18.1%	3,340	14.1%	3.5%
25	4,497	22.8%	2,927	19.1%	3.1%
26	3,663	27.1%	2,457	23.7%	2.8%
27	2,882		1,987		
Ave		14.2%		11.8%	2.1%

Chart 4 - Energy, cooling hours and heat exchange, %/°C – Tel Aviv [5]

Average Change in Range 26°C-22°C

Table 5 - Average change in range 26°C-22°C - Jerusalem

Cool On °C	ECW kWh/y	ΔE%/°C	hrC hr/y	Δhr%/°C	ΔHX%/°C
22	2,884	36.8%	2,702	27.2%	7.5%
23	2,108	42.2%	2,124	30.1%	9.3%
24	1,482	49.7%	1,632	38.5%	8.1%
25	990	66.4%	1,178	48.0%	12.4%
26	595		796		
Ave		48.8%		36.0%	9.3%

Table 6 - Average change in range 26°C-22°C – Tel Aviv

Cool On °C	ECW kWh/y	ΔE%/°C	hrC hr/y	Δhr%/°C	ΔHX%/°C
22	7,007	14.1%	4,177	11.4%	2.4%
23	6,139	15.6%	3,749	12.2%	3.0%
24	5,309	18.1%	3,340	14.1%	3.5%
25	4,497	22.8%	2,927	19.1%	3.1%
26	3,663		2,457		
Ave		17.6%		14.2%	3.0%

Table 7 - Average change in range 26°C-22°C – Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

Cool On °C	Jerusalem	Tel Aviv	Ave
22	36.8%	14.1%	25.5%
23	42.2%	15.6%	28.9%
24	49.7%	18.1%	33.9%
25	66.4%	22.8%	44.6%
26			
Ave	48.8%	17.6%	33.2%

Table 8 - Average increase in air conditioning energy consumption with each Centigrade in range 26°C-22°C – Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

Average ΔE%/°C Jerusalem and Tel Aviv in range 26°C-22°C	33.2%	per 1°C
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References

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